

Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research grant project "Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology" Izp-2025/1-0191 (2026-2028).

This interdisciplinary research project explores the readiness of citizens in Latvia, Estonia and Lithuania to identify and report suspicious activities in the face of hybrid threats. Positioned at a geopolitical frontline, the Baltic States must foster whole-of-society resilience, especially as threats span cyberattacks, disinformation, and sabotage. The project investigates how political, legal, psychological, and technological factors shape public engagement in comprehensive defense. Drawing on social control theory and international best practices, it assesses public understanding of suspicious activity and evaluates the effectiveness of current reporting mechanisms, including digital platforms. A mixed-methods approach will be used, and survey data produced. The study aims to inform policies that empower individuals, strengthen societal trust, improve legal structures, and guide the development of accessible and effective digital tools. Ultimately, the project contributes to academic knowledge and practical policymaking by offering actionable recommendations to enhance individual-driven security, ensuring the Baltic States are better prepared to identify and confront complex security challenges.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Empowering Baltic Resilience:
From Awareness to Action via
Technology

Researchers

Roberts Kits (0000-0002-8682-3731), Ieva Birka (0000-0002-4453-7825), aleksandrs kolesovs (0000-0003-4470-2453), Irena Barkane (0000-0003-2555-3667), Didzis Kļaviņš (0000-0002-9096-6719)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research grant project "Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology" lzp-2025/1-0191 (2026-2028).

This interdisciplinary research project explores the readiness of citizens in Latvia, Estonia and Lithuania to identify and report suspicious activities in the face of hybrid threats. Positioned at a geopolitical frontline, the Baltic States must foster whole-of-society resilience, especially as threats span cyberattacks, disinformation, and sabotage. The project investigates how political, legal, psychological, and technological factors shape public engagement in comprehensive defense. Drawing on social control theory and international best practices, it assesses public understanding of suspicious activity and evaluates the effectiveness of current reporting mechanisms, including digital platforms. A mixed-methods approach will be used, and survey data produced. The study aims to inform policies that empower individuals, strengthen societal trust, improve legal structures, and guide the development of accessible and effective digital tools. Ultimately, the project contributes to academic knowledge and practical policymaking by offering actionable recommendations to enhance individual-driven security, ensuring the Baltic States are better prepared to identify and confront complex security challenges.

Researchers:

[Roberts Kits \(0000-0002-8682-3731\)](#)

[Ieva Birka \(0000-0002-4453-7825\)](#)

[aleksandrs kolesovs \(0000-0003-4470-2453\)](#)

[Irena Barkane \(0000-0003-2555-3667\)](#)

[Didzis Kļaviņš \(0000-0002-9096-6719\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [BIRKA IEVA \(ieva.birka@lu.lv\)](mailto:IEVA.BIRKA@LU.LV)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science | | LCS](#)

Grants: [Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology](#)

Project: [Empowering Baltic Resilience: From Awareness to Action via Technology](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-02-17](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Survey results on suspicious activity reporting Baltic capitals](#)

The project will generate a comprehensive, cross-national dataset based on a representative survey conducted in Tallinn, Riga, and Vilnius, with at least 1,000 respondents in each city.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data will capture psychological, social, political, legal, and technological dimensions of individuals' ability to recognize and report suspicious or unusual activities in a hybrid-threat environment. The survey will include national-language translations and employ representative sampling, ensuring balanced inclusion of

age groups, genders, and minorities. All responses will be cleaned and prepared in SPSS and Excel formats.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- SAV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

For the project needs, current data is needed to ascertain the current situation, and no such existing data set currently exists looking at suspicious activity reporting.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The planned dataset will be valuable to a wide range of actors working in the fields of national security, crisis preparedness, hybrid-threat mitigation, and societal resilience. In particular, the data will be useful for:

National crisis management authorities in Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania seeking evidence-based insights into public awareness, behavioral barriers, and reporting readiness.

Security, defense, and intelligence institutions, including state security services and national threat-assessment bodies, who need population-level data on early-warning behaviors and suspicious-activity recognition.

Legal and regulatory institutions working on balancing security measures with civil liberties, privacy, and human rights protections.

Municipal authorities responsible for community resilience, local policing, civil protection, and public-awareness initiatives.

Technology developers and digital-innovation actors designing or improving apps and tools for citizen reporting, early warning, or crisis communication.

Researchers in psychology, political science, law, and security studies studying threat perception, social behavior, trust, participation, and hybrid-threat environments.

International organizations such as NATO COEs, Hybrid CoE, and EU institutions exploring citizen engagement and comprehensive-defense concepts.

Civil society and NGOs focused on community safety, inclusion, minority protection, and public-awareness campaigns.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

We plan to provide full metadata for all collected data. The metadata will follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and will include:

Description of the dataset structure and variables

Survey methodology (sampling frame, weighting, translations, fieldwork details)

Questionnaire and codebook

Data-cleaning and coding procedures

Information on representativeness (age, gender, region, minority groups)

Documentation of focus group protocols and transcripts

File formats (SPSS, Excel) and versioning

Ethical and data-protection considerations

This metadata will ensure that the dataset can be efficiently used by researchers, policymakers, crisis-management authorities, legal analysts, and technology developers, as well as integrated into long-term research and intervention planning.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Comment:

Yes, until the end of the research project 30.12.2028.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

The DataverseLV repository is a secure platform for long-term preservation and publication of research data. University of Latvia is part of the platform.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel; SPSS.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The dataset will be delivered in SPSS (.sav) and Excel (.xlsx) formats, ensuring compatibility with both statistical software and standard office tools. The SPSS file will include variable labels, value labels, and embedded metadata, while the Excel version will contain clean, structured sheets with variable names and coding

instructions. Accompanying materials—such as the questionnaire, codebook, focus group transcripts, and methodological documentation—will be provided in PDF and Word (.docx) formats. This structure ensures that users can easily analyze, reproduce, and integrate the data into qualitative or quantitative workflows.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2034-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ieva Birka (0000-0002-4453-7825)

Data preparation will require time dedicated to organizing, anonymizing, and creating detailed metadata. There will also be time spent ensuring adherence to FAIR principles and ethical standards. Training time will also be allocated for the research team to train on FAIR data practices and use of repositories. These efforts will ensure that the project data remains discoverable, accessible under consented conditions, and usable for future research.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

All data will be stored and processed within the secure IT infrastructure of the University of Latvia, using a combination of technical and organizational safeguards to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and controlled access. Security measures include:

Password-protected access to all datasets, storage folders, and analysis environments.

Firewall-protected servers provided by the university to prevent unauthorized external access.

Role-based personal access control, ensuring that only authorized project team members can view, edit, or download the data.

Encrypted file transfer (e.g., via secured university channels) to prevent interception during data exchange.

Secure storage on institutional servers, not on personal devices, except where encrypted and approved.

Regular backups on protected university systems to avoid data loss.

Anonymization of all personal or sensitive information before analysis or sharing, ensuring compliance with GDPR and ethical standards.

These measures jointly ensure that all data is protected throughout collection, storage, analysis, and dissemination.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

